

Participant No.

To include recruiting partner acronym e.g. CU1, CTU3, BIU9, TIL20, etc.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM: PARENT GUARDIAN UNDER-18 **Citizen Scientists Investigating Cookies and App GDPR compliance (CSI-COP)**

Thank you for consenting to your child completing CSI-COP's free informal education course/MOOC 'Your Right to Privacy Online' and for expressing interest in their joining this research study for the purpose of investigating cookies in websites and apps.

Before you consent to your child taking part, you must **read the accompanying Participant Information Sheet.**

Please do not hesitate to ask questions if anything is unclear or if you would like more information about any aspect of this research. It is important that you feel able to take the necessary time to decide whether or not your child should take part.

If you are happy for your child to participate, please confirm your consent by circling YES against each of the statements below and then signing and dating the form as a CSI-COP project participant.

1	I confirm that I have read and understood the <u>Participant Information Sheet</u> for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions	YES	NO
2	I understand the participation of an under 18 participant in my care is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw their data, without giving a reason, by contacting Dr Huma Shah on ab7778@coventry.ac.uk <u>at any time</u> until the date specified in the Participant Information Sheet	YES	NO
3	I have noted down the participant number (top left of this Consent Form) which may be required by Coventry University if I wish to withdraw my child from the study	YES	NO
4	I understand that all the information I provide on my child will be held securely and treated confidentially	YES	NO
5	I am happy for the information I provide to be used anonymously in academic papers and other formal research outputs	YES	NO
6	I agree for my child to take part in the above study	YES	NO

Thank you for consenting to you your child to participate in this study. This contribution is very much appreciated.

Participant's Name	Date	Signature
CSI-COP Researcher	Date	Signature

